

PHENET
 PHENOTYPING & ENVIROTYPING
 SOLUTIONS FOR AGROECOLOGY

TOOLS AND METHODS FOR EXTENDED PLANT PHENOTYPING AND ENVIROTYPING SERVICES OF EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

Deliverable 6.1

Deliverable *Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan*

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1 SUMMARY

1.1 OBJECTIVES

Deliverable 6.1 depicts a plan for communication, dissemination and exploitation of the PHENET project, provided by WP6 (“Maximising Impact through Outreach, Training and Communication”).

1.2 RATIONALE

While D6.1 describes in general terms the aims, conceptual approach, addressees, and portfolio of instruments over the 5 years of the project, it becomes more specific in terms of concrete planned work activities within the first 18 months of PHENET. We understand this deliverable as a living document, which will be regularly updated in cooperation with WP6 and the other WPs to integrate the latest developments regarding and within all PHENET WPs, regarding its stakeholder groups, available communication instruments, and “lessons learned”. As such, this Deliverable provides also a general guideline for communication, dissemination and exploitation for the 5 years to come, leading to concrete action plans (and key performance indicators) for the period after the first 18 months.

1.3 TEAMS INVOLVED

The development of D6.1 has been coordinated by Work Package 6, primarily by task 6.3. The concrete actions described will be performed by all PHENET partners while being coordinated jointly by task 6.2 (on exploitation) and task 6.3 (on communication and dissemination). The further development of the CDEP as a living document will be coordinated by task 6.3 and involve all PHENET partners.

2 COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION AIMS

PHENET's Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Activities (CDEAs) are key supporting activities for the project's six objectives, which aim to equip Research Infrastructures (RIs) with innovative services that increase their capacity to future-proof agroecosystems, i.e:

1. Co-develop with industry, new, environment-friendly, low-cost, AI-based, automated and connected devices gathering sets of sensors able to capture a large diversity of traits (phenotyping), environmental variables (envirotyping) and processes in agroecosystems, in particular related to the agroecological transition and climate change (e.g. soil carbon, biodiversity, plant biotic stress tolerance...).
2. Develop digital solutions for multi-scale data analytics, connecting phenotypic and environmental information from the plant level to the field and the landscape, in particular leveraging on earth observation (EO) services.
3. Provide data integration tools for multiple sources of information (sensors at various scales, EO, databases and literature). Implement methods for data interoperability with models. Promote tools for data-based knowledge and their reuse by European research communities.
4. Develop and implement digital twins, process based, AI or statistical modelling solutions, leveraging on phenotypic and environmental data, in support to the analysis and the prediction of the interaction between Species or Genotypes, Environments and Management practices (S/G x E x M).
5. Demonstrate, through a series of UCs, tackling concrete bottlenecks in different agroecosystems, the applicability of tools and methods developed by methodological WPs. Mobilising the largest

range of phenotypic and environmental data including on-farm trials and thereby develop joint services by the communities through tight integration and representation of all RIs in the project.

6. Develop across all RIs committed (i) sustained training activities towards a new generation of scientists, engineers and technicians, able to use and refine the advanced tools and methods developed within PHENET, and (ii) outreaching activities leveraging on networks, living labs or stakeholder groups associated with each Use Case (UC).

CDEAs will help to maximize the impact of their contribution to PHENET's twelve key outcomes (see also PHENET Grant Agreement, Annex I) through stakeholder appropriate communication and dissemination, and help to exploit PHENET's next generation technologies resulting from the use cases in WP1 and the more generic tools and methods from WP2 - 6.

In that context, CDEAs aim at:

- Increasing the user base of the RIs service portfolios (AnaEE¹, eLTER², ELIXIR³, EMPHASIS⁴) well beyond the project lifetime.
- Enhancing collaboration in Europe around PHENET next generation technologies and related RI services.
- Building a trainer community around PHENET next generation technologies.
- Supporting SMEs operating close or within agriculture and agroecology-related markets to strengthen the impact of their businesses.
- Integrating PHENET next generation technologies in RI service portfolios beyond the four PHENET RI partners.
- Fostering cross-fertilisation around PHENET next generation technologies by engaging existing and upcoming Living Labs and further innovation hubs (local, regional, national).
- Supporting policy makers and further high-level decision makers with evidence-based knowledge on future-proof agroecosystems.
- Increasing the acceptance of sustainable agriculture and agroecosystem management with the broader public.

In working towards these aims, PHENET will build trust, bonding, and advocacy for RI services according to a conceptual approach depicted in Figure 1. While trust, bonding and advocacy will build on the concrete experiences RIs and their users will make when dealing with PHENET partners (which is not directly formable by the CDEAs), PHENET communication will lay the foundation for successfully generating advocacy by establishing the PHENET brand and its equity. In the long term (= beyond the PHENET lifetime), PHENET brand and PHENET communication will be understood as a tool to generate advocacy of the users with the RIs and their services, as they will support PHENET and its products.

¹ https://www.phenet.eu/en/about_parterning_ris/a_n_aee

² https://www.phenet.eu/en/about_parterning_ris/e_lter

³ https://www.phenet.eu/en/about_parterning_ris/elixir

⁴ https://www.phenet.eu/en/about_parterning_ris/emphasis

Figure 1: A conceptual pipeline towards building advocacy towards research infrastructure services (presented by Andrea Alemanno, IPSOS, at the Executive Master for Research Infrastructures, University Milano-Bicocca, 2019).

3 PHENET STAKEHOLDERS

PHENET contributes to a wide range of policy agendas (e.g. Green Deal, “Soil Deal for Europe” mission, FOOD 2030) and key societal challenges (climate change mitigation, climate change adaptation, food security, biodiversity sustainability), works to address a wide range of scientific challenges (e.g. overcoming the phenotyping bottleneck, providing technologies for acquiring and using envirotyping and phenotyping data, platforms for FAIR data sharing of those data), and will update RI service portfolio with its “next generation technologies” (NGTs).

By doing so, the project addresses a large diversity of stakeholders. Regarding NGTs, here we understand all tools, methods and technologies which are being further developed within the PHENET Use Cases in WP1 and in the more generic WP 2-5. Figure 2 provides a general overview on PHENET stakeholders and the communication channels that PHENET operates.

PHENET STAKEHOLDERS & END-USERS		CHANNELS														
		Scientific publications	Scientific conferences	Hackathons	Train-the-trainer sessions	Online courses	IPPN webinars	Scientific workshops	Exhibitions	Policy briefs	Service point for business	Living labs	Business Briefs	Social media	Newsletter	Websites
Circle 1: RI Users	Research Infrastructures (U)															
	RI service users (U)															
	Senior Researchers (U, SH)															
	Early career scientists, students (U, SH)															
	Technicians, engineers (U, SH)															
Circle 2: Stakeholders	Industry															
	-seed breeding companies (U, SH)															
	-crop protection companies (U, SH)															
	-extension services (SH)															
	-techno providers (hardware & software) (SH)															
	-digital services providers (SH)															
	-cooperatives and other farming consultants (U, SH)															
	-Biostimulant/biocontrol companies (U, SH)															
	Other															
	Farmers (U, SH)															
Circle 3	Broader public (SH)															

* Examination Offices, Post-Registration Org.
U, SH : priority targets

■ Main sources □ Complementary sources

Figure 2: General overview of PHENET stakeholder groups and PHENET communication channels.

PHENET stakeholders comprise three (partly overlapping) target groups:

1. The four research infrastructures directly participating in PHENET (AnaEE, eLTER, ELIXIR, EMPHASIS), their staff being directly employed at these RIs, their staff being employed at the RI facilities, and the users of their services, with all these groups spanning all career levels. PHENET also intends to reach out to RIs which are not directly part of the PHENET consortia, but also neighbouring RIs, which could have an interest to integrate PHENET technologies into their service portfolios. PHENET aims at a successful pick-up and integration of its technologies into the RI operational service portfolios and at attracting users to them.
2. Stakeholders in the wider environment of the RIs, who have a stake in the scientific topics and the political agendas to which PHENET contributes. This group has a very wide diversity, spans multiple business-related domains, and covers a huge area of stakes involved. A major part therein constitutes companies and businesses with their different business models, products, and services in the fields of breeding, crop protection, biostimulants, farming and extension services, but also covering technology providers for sensors, imaging, data management, data analysis and data visualization. These businesses are complemented by further business-related stakeholders, which form the financial and regulatory frameworks for these companies. PHENET aims to support the business models of these companies with its competencies and technologies, and to improve the regulatory and financial frameworks for the exploitation of these technologies.
3. The broader public is in numbers and in respect to diversity by far the largest group to be addressed by PHENET communication. PHENET aims to raise awareness about the benefits of the RI services in general, and specifically about the PHENET technologies and their contribution to solutions for the greater societal challenges ahead.

4 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

PHENET operates a wide range of communication channels specifically adapted towards the different stakeholder groups (see also **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**), being coordinated and supported by Task 6.3:

- Scientific publications will be a core channel to inform scientists from stakeholder groups 1 & 2 about the scientific discoveries and progress made in WP1 – 5 or PHENET: this activity will mainly build on the reputation and networks that PHENET scientists have already built in their respective communities in these WPs and will be supported by Task 6.3 by ensuring open access publication on other platforms where adequate (e.g. zenodo).
- Scientific conferences and scientific workshops will be a key platform for PHENET scientists to discuss, to get and collect feedback for their findings from a wider community, and to inform and discuss with the users of the technologies. While the presentation of the scientific results will be in the hands of the WP1 – 5 scientists in their role as PHENET ambassadors, Task 6.2 will support them by providing basic presentation material about PHENET, by providing information about potential conferences outside the existing networks (e.g. annual meetings of neighbouring RIs), and by organising additional scientific sessions at conferences from interested communities (specifically at the International Plant Phenotyping Conferences⁵ 2024 and 2026).
- Hackathons, as understood by the PHENET partners, are large-scale events that provide a platform to bring together researchers, mainly at an early stage of their careers, and foster collaboration by working together on very specific challenges. PHENET hackathons will focus on the development of bioinformatic tools and methods for data management, modelling and visualization and will contribute to the PHENET goals by (1) concretely developing such tools and thus increasing their TRLs, (2) training researchers from RIs on these tools and thus facilitating the long-term integration of these technologies into their service portfolios, (3) involving users of these technologies already in the development phase and thus increasing the RI user base. PHENET will organize one European hackathons with the aim of attracting at least 50 participants.
- Train-the-trainer sessions can be very helpful for PHENET partners in several ways. These sessions are designed to provide participants with the knowledge, skills, and tools needed to design and deliver effective training programs. A train-the-trainer session can provide the tools and techniques to deliver engaging and effective presentations and more targeted training. Train-the-trainer sessions can provide insight into active learning strategies to ensure that the audience is engaged in the learning process.
- Online and in-person training for PHENET partners can provide individuals with a wealth of knowledge and skills necessary to enhance their research in these areas. In general, courses for plant phenotyping research can cover a variety of topics, such as data analysis tools / techniques, data management and machine learning and artificial intelligence in plant phenotyping research. Some training programmes may include a combination of lectures, assignments, and webinars delivered by experts in the field. Participants will also have the opportunity to interact with experts

⁵ https://www.plant-phenotyping.org/Previous_Symposia

and other programme participants to share experiences and ask questions. It is important to note that online training in plant phenotyping research can differ in terms of learning outcomes, format, duration, and cost. It is advisable to carefully evaluate various programmes to determine the best fit for your specific needs and circumstances.

- Phenomics webinars⁶, established jointly by IPPN and EMPHASIS, are a well-established community-driven communication instruments primarily providing benefits to the scientific communities about plant phenotyping. These webinars have been established as a joint activity between the International Plant Phenotyping Network⁷ and the RI EMPHASIS in 2020 as platform to present and exchange on latest scientific developments. This series has seen almost 30 webinars (unit June 2023), with up to 520 scientists from industry and academia participating in and viewing each seminar.
- Policy briefs will inform policy makers on national and European level about the benefits of PHENET technologies and about the RIs involved but will also provide recommendations on how to improve policy frameworks towards fostering agroecology and future agricultural systems. PHENET aims at providing at least two policy briefs based on the PHENET progress. It will provide these briefs to the participating RIs and their General Assembly to inform policy makers directly involved as legal owners of the RIs. To further increase the impact, PHENET will collaborate with well-established initiatives in the research infrastructure, the agroecology and agricultural landscape, including Life-Science RIs⁸, Envri⁹, ERIC-Forum¹⁰, and ENRIITC¹¹, where PHENET representatives will provide their expertise also in further activities from these initiatives addressing policy makers. The policy briefs will also be made public via the digital communication channels of the project. Next to policy briefs, PHENET members are already engaged on an individual level in policy advice functions (currently = June 2023 towards European Food Safety Authority, towards French and German Ministry of Agriculture, towards Chambers of Agriculture in Austria and Germany) where they will continue and integrate PHENET developments.
- PHENET research infrastructure already collaborate or partner with existing or upcoming Living Labs which are potential platforms for further NGT co-development and / or application of NGTs in real world scenarios (All-Ready network¹², AgroServ¹³, ECO-Ready¹⁴). PHENET WP6 will build on these connections and identify most suitable LLs for concrete collaboration and integration of NGTs.
- Business briefs will present opportunities on PHENET NGT towards business-related stakeholders and thus help to raise awareness and kick-start engagement with them. PHENET will provide at least 2 business briefs over the time of the project.
- The PHENET website¹⁵ (operated by task 6.3) functions as a main information hub about all kind of PHENET activities and as gateway to PHENET in the digital world. It provides basic information on PHENET, its mission, aims, scope, and partnership and will provide up-to-date information on

⁶ <https://www.plant-phenotyping.org/index.php?index=877>

⁷ https://www.plant-phenotyping.org/IPPN_home

⁸ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/home.html>

⁹ <https://envri.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://www.eric-forum.eu/>

¹¹ <https://enriitc.eu/>

¹² <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/>

¹³ <https://agroserv.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://www.eco-ready.eu/living-labs/>

¹⁵ <https://www.phenet.eu/en>

PHENET developments. Its structure is stakeholder-related and aims to provide an easy gateway for the diversity stakeholder communities towards the information they require most. Next to providing updates on news and events about PHENET and partnering initiatives, on agroecology, on agriculture and on research infrastructures, it holds repositories on PHENET public deliverables, on available training materials, on its newsletters and on its policy briefs. It further provides links to relevant initiatives around PHENET, to the four participating infrastructures and to partnering initiatives. The information provided on the website (and on the social media and newsletter) will be aligned with the information provided by the four participating RIs, in concrete terms by on-going exchange between task 6.2 and the communication offices of the RIs. In the long-term, the website (as well as the social media channels) will be sustained by the communication offices of the four partnering infrastructures and integrated into their communication activities.

- PHENET social media channels comprise currently (=June 2023) LinkedIn¹⁶ and Twitter¹⁷. These channels will primarily be used to provide latest updates on PHENET and partnering initiatives and link to the PHENET website, the websites of the four partnering research infrastructures, and to further available online sources for more detailed information. PHENET will run specific social media campaigns in advertising its own events or its participation in events on these channels. With communication technologies developing rapidly, this set of social media communication channels will be under constant review by Task 6.3, and further channels may be established in line with the overall PHENET developments.
- The first newsletter will be provided in summer 2023 (coordinated by task 6.3), depicting basic information about PHENET and where to find further information, providing updates from the four participating RIs, and further updates from the broader community (e.g. events of interest). PHENET aims at providing at least two newsletters a year, complementing the information provided already on the website and the PHENET social media channels. Additionally, PHENET will provide “flash newsletters” which will inform on specific developments or events of interest. Newsletter content will be strongly aligned with the newsletters provided by communication offices of the participating RIs.

5 EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES

PHENET will operate a project-specific “Innovation Management Group” (IMG), which holds responsibility for:

- Providing strategic advice and expertise support towards the PHENET ExCom on all areas around exploitation via developing respective strategies on these topics, and therein developing and suggesting concrete activities fostering PHENET impact.
- Developing and regularly revising an Innovation Management Group Action Plan to that end.
- Providing a dedicated platform within PHENET to share expertise, knowledge, experiences, and ideas on exploitation and thus help to further build capacities on these topics within PHENET and within the four partnering RIs.

¹⁶ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/phenet>

¹⁷ https://twitter.com/phenet_project

The IGM will specifically deal with the following topics (and further fields of interest to be developed over the lifetime of the project):

- Collaboration with existing and future Living Labs in fields of interest (e.g. AgroServ Living Labs, ALL-Ready Living Labs, Occitanum, Vegepolys-valley, Doller valley, Tereno)
- Collaboration with Extension services (e.g. Arvalis)
- Collaboration with neighbouring research infrastructures and RI initiatives
- Engagement of farmers, plant breeders and further businesses around agriculture
- Engagement of investors and funders (e.g. Rabobank)
- Engagement of regulators (e.g. Landwirtschaftskammer Österreich (LKO))

The IMG will thus complement the concrete PHENET-industry collaborations already taking place in the Use Cases and in the WP2 – 5 by establishing its strategic scope. It will consist of 5 -6 experts in the field of innovation from PHENET partners (spanning WPs and RIs) as core team, being coordinated by task 6.2. Next to this core team, it will establish an open digital collaborative space enabling all persons involved in PHENET to contribute, to share their ideas and to jointly support the strategic work of the core team, while at the same time fostering commitment and intrinsic motivation towards exploitation within the project. The IGM will further seek to integrate external expertise (= beyond PHENET) for specific cases. The IGM will meet at least quarterly (mainly virtually), with the open digital space being in use 24 / 7. It will develop its own work plan in line with its general scope and in close alignment with the PHENET ExCom.

6 RISK MANAGEMENT

PHENET has implemented a portfolio of measures to ensure that risks related to communication, dissemination and exploitation are timely identified and assessed and to have potential mitigation measures prepared and ready in advance to any risk manifesting. These include:

- WP6 leads to monitor risks as described in Table 1 and update the identified risks and their assessment on a quarterly basis. If one of those risks starts manifesting, WP6 will implement the pre-defined mitigation measures in close collaboration with the ExCom and the Coordination.
- WP6 leads to check KPI developments against the target values on a quarterly basis (**Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**) and modify CDPAs to ensure future respective performance. If adaption or mitigation is needed, WP6 leads will operate these modifications in close collaboration with the Coordination and the ExCom.
- WP6 leads reporting on the realisation of CDEP to the PHENET scientific leads (= ExCom) in regular meetings and integrating their feedback into its activities.
- WP6 leads reporting to the Scientific Advisory Board according to the reporting lines defined within the project and integrating the given advice and recommendations into its activities.

7 ANNEXES

7.1 COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION RISK REGISTRY

Table 1: Risk registry including assessments (1: very low; 5: very high) and potential mitigation measures.

No	Risk description	Assessment		Mitigation measures
		Probability	Impact	
1	Unexpected long-term absence of persons in charge of CDEAs in WP6 (e.g. illness)	3	5	Re-shifting of tasks (1) internally of the host institution (2) within WP6 (3) within the consortium
2	CDEAs fail to meet stakeholders' demands	2	5	Thorough stakeholder demand mapping before engagement activities take place; if realised while activities take place, adaptation, and re-arrangement by WP6 leads
3	Decrease or complete absence of communication activities taking place at the 4 partnering RIs	1	4	Compensation by partly integrating RI stakeholders as direct addresses into PHENET communication channels (e.g. social media). Fostering direct discussion with RI coordinators to exchange on future joint activities.
4	Lack of support for PHENET scientists to act as PHENET ambassadors	2	4	Fostering direct interaction, identifying needs and demands, providing additional knowledge & information & material.
5	Need for further expertise around exploitation	3	3	Identification of demands within Innovation Management Group; identification of respective external expertise and connection to IMG

No	Risk description	Assessment		Mitigation measures
6	Need to raise awareness on the relevance and benefits of exploitation with all persons involved in PHENET (specifically young researchers)	4	2	Integration into Open digital collaborative space of Innovation Management Group
7	Working on rather unspecific exploitation aims	3	4	Foster strategic discussions in Innovation Management Group and narrow the results down to specific actions

7.2 COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION ACTION PLAN FOR THE FIRST 18 MONTHS (JAN 2023 – JUNE 2024)

Table 2: Action Plan for the first 18 months of PHENET

Aim	Target Group	Instrument	Who	Until when (=month)
Establish and operate Innovation Management Group	Internal and external stakeholders on innovation	Innovation Management Group	Task 6.2	12
Scientific progress on NGTs	Scientists (academia & industry)	Scientific publications	WP 1 - 5	18
Scientific progress on NGTs; attract future RI users	Scientists (academia & industry)	Presentation at scientific conferences or workshops (presentations, posters)	WP 1 - 5	18
Provide an event where scientists can meet, discuss, and implement ideas and projects through intensive and productive (coding) sessions	Scientists (academia & industry)	Organisation of 1 Hackathon	Task 6.1	18
Build a trainer community around NGTs; Training of additional trainers in PHENET; Improving teaching skills	Trainer and scientists (academia & industry) interested in training	Organisation of Train-the-trainer-sessions	Task 6.1	18

Aim	Target Group	Instrument	Who	Until when (=month)
Training of scientists	Scientists (academia & industry)	Organisation of training courses (online / face to face learning)	Task 6.1	18
Scientific progress on NGTs; attract future RI users	Scientists (academia & industry)	Presentation at 1 IPPN webinars	Task 6.2	18
Raise awareness on PHENET (and RIs) with businesses, regulators and funders	Business-related stakeholders	Presentation at 1 Exhibition	Task 6.2	18
Raise awareness on PHENET (and RIs) with policy decision-makers	Policy makers	Publication of 1 policy brief	Task 6.2	12
Provide decision-supporting analysis on adequacy of LLs for intensified collaboration	Living Labs	Analyse existing and upcoming LLs	Task 6.2	18
Raise awareness on PHENET (and RIs) with businesses, regulators and funders	Business-Related stakeholders	Publication of 1 Business Briefs	Task 6.2	18
Raise awareness on PHENET (and RIs)	All stakeholders	Outreach via social media	Task 6.3	Ongoing
Raise awareness on PHENET (and RIs)	All stakeholders	Outreach via newsletter	Task 6.3	Ongoing
Raise awareness on PHENET (and RIs)	All stakeholders	Outreach via website	Task 6.3	Ongoing